

A number of conjectures are likely to setup

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ABSTRACT

An unresolved conjecture in number theory has great possibility to set up.

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INTRODUCTION:

Have an unresolved conjecture in number theory,

$Q_1=2, q_2=3, q_3=5, Q_4, Q_5, \dots$, from small to large order write all the prime numbers,

$Q_k=q_1*q_2*q_3, \dots, q_{k+1}$

$Q_1=3, Q_2=7, Q_3=31, Q_4=211, Q_5=2311, Q_6=59*509,$

$Q_7=19*97*277, Q_8=347*27953, Q_9=317*7037$

$63, Q_{10}=331*571*34231$

The number five is a prime number, after the number five is a composite number, there is now a question of whether there are infinitely many k such that Q_k is a prime number, or the Q_k number?

Look at a matrix:

In 1934, East India (now Bangladesh) Chandra proposed a square sieve:

The first line is the first of 4, 3 of the tolerance of arithmetic sequence $4, 7, 10, \dots, 4+3(n-1), \dots$

The second line is the first of 7, 5 of the tolerance of arithmetic sequence $7, 12, 17, \dots, 7+5(n-1), \dots$

The third line is the first of 10, 7 of the tolerance of arithmetic sequence $10, 17, 24, \dots, 10+7(n-1), \dots$

The fourth line is the first of 13, 9 of the tolerance of arithmetic sequence $13, 22, 31, \dots, 13+9(n-1), \dots$

Line m is the first $3m+1$, tolerance of arithmetic sequence $2m+1, 3m+1, 5m+2, 7m+3, \dots$, its n item is $3m+1+(n-1)(2m+1)=2mn+m+n, \dots$

Write the following array:

First column, second column, third column, fourth column, fifth column... Column n...

First row 47101316... $4+3(n-1)$...
 Second row 712172227... $7+5(n-1)$...
 Third row 1017243138... $10+7(n-1)$...
 Fourth row 1322314049... $13+9(n-1)$...
 Fifth row 1627384960... $16+11(n-1)$...

Line $3m+1$ $5m+2$ $7m+3$ $9m+4$ $11m+5$ m... $2mn+m+n$...

The secret lies in this square: if a natural number N appears in the table, then $2N + 1$ is certainly not a prime number; if N does not appear in the table, then $2N + 1$ is certainly a prime number.

In fact, if $N=2mn+m+n$, then $2N+1=2(2mn+m+n)+1=4mn+2m+2n+1=(2m+1)(2n+1)$, it is not prime. On

the contrary, the N does not appear in the table, if $2N+1$ is not a prime number, then $2N+1$ must be a product of two odd, write $2N+1=(2m+1)(2n+1)=4mn+2m+2n+1$, $N=2mn+m+n$, it appears in the table, with the assumption of contradiction. So when N does not appear in the matrix when $2N+1$ is a prime number.

$Q_k=q_1*q_2*q_3, \dots, *q_{k+1}$, $q_1=2$, so $Q_2=2*(q_2*q_3, \dots, Q_k)+1$, apparently $q_2*q_3*q_4, \dots, *q_k$

Is the number, so $q_2*q_3*q_4, *q_k=2N+1$, N, and the above parties appear in the screen, appearing in square sieve in N has an infinite number if the $2N+1$ appear or do not appear in the matrix. Then it has an infinite number of the $Q_k=2*(2N+1)+1$ is prime or composite.

So this conjecture is likely to be established!

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